

Formulation and evaluation of neem soap

Dhara Mohanbhai Jadav* and Ravi Sureshbhai Bhayani

School of Pharmacy, Sabarmati University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India.

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Abstract

A local herb known as neem (semambu) or its scientific name *Azadirachta indica* has been used extensively in traditional treatment due to its medicinal properties. Neem powder have been used traditionally for treating several epidermal dysfunctions, such as eczema, psoriasis, and acne. Neem is rich in antioxidants and helps to boost immune response in tissues of affected skin area. It also consists of bioactive compounds for antibacterial, antifungal, and anticancer activities. In this study, neem leaves extract was used in producing herbal neem soap as a remedy for curing skin problems. The herbal neem soap was made by blending 36.4% palm oil, 9.1% coconut oil, 27.3% sodium hydroxide, 9.1% neem powder extract, and 18.2% neem aqueous extract which formed a pale yellow soap base. The results of the selected physical and chemical properties of this study show that the moisture content of the soap was 4.02% with 10.60 pH value, 57.40% total fatty matter, and 0.44% free caustic alkali. The results imply that herbal neem soap is suitable for human skin and can be a therapeutic alternative to skin problems.

Keywords: *Azadirachta indica*; Herbal soap; Formulation; Skin problems

1. Introduction

Human skin, the outer covering of the body constitutes the first line of defense protecting the body against various pathogens. As the skin interfaces with environment, it is constantly exposed to different environmental stimuli. This makes the skin damage prone. Severely damaged skin will often try to heal by forming scar tissue, which is often decolorized and depigmented. Plants have been used in the treatment of human diseases and infections since ages. The active constituents of plants can be formulated as ointment, cream, gel, lotion, soap, or crude/solvent extract. Utilization of plant extracts and their derived phytoconstituents have a likely future for controlling hyperpigmentation. Plant-based remedies mentioned in ayurvedic texts are gaining popularity these days in India due to validation of such therapies with respect to their modern counterparts. Soaps are one among the modern-day cosmetics for maintaining and enhancing the vigor of skin. However, the present chemical soaps quite frequently can cause dryness and irritation of the skin. Interestingly, the popularity of herbal-based soaps is increasing due to their efficacy on topical disorders. The plants that mentioned under varnya herbs in Ayurveda and their modern counterpart, i.e., tyrosinase inhibition is also proven.

2. Ingredients

- Neem Powder 5G M
- Castor Oil 16 Ml
- Palm Oil 22Ml
- Coconut Oil 16Ml
- Lye (Sodium Hydroxide) 7.5Gm
- Distilled Water 50Ml

* Corresponding author: Dhara Mohanbhai Jadav

- Essential Oil Or Fragrance Oil 5 Drops 5

3. Equipment's

- Use only steel or glass containers.
- Don't use aluminium or plastic containers.
- Stick blender.
- Utensils which are used for saponification cannot be used in the kitchen.
- Silicone moulds.
- Soap cutter.
- Peeler to give finishing to the soap.
- Temperature gun.

4. Procedure and parameters

- Measure the lye and distilled water in different containers.
- Quantity of lye should always be less than distilled water taken
- Add small quantity of lye to the distilled water slowly
- Exothermic reaction
- Stir it well
- Keep the mixture to cool down till we get the temperature
- Measure the temperature
- Now start measuring the oils and butters
- Butters or solid oils should be melted
- Mix all the butters and oils according to the recipe
- Now pour the lye water solution in the oil mixture
- Mix it well
- Now blend it for till you get thick consistency
- Trace point
- Now add the additives fo , eo, herb powders , colours
- Mix it well
- Prepare your mould , wooden mould should be covered with butter paper
- Spray rubbing alcohol in the mould before pouring
- Again spray rubbing alcohol after pouring
- Cover the soap with cloth
- If added juice / milk don't cover the soap , keep it open
- Keep the soap in dark , dry place for 24 hours
- Now unmould the soap and cut it

4.1. Curing

The unmoulded soap needs to cure for 4-6 weeks

- While curing soap should be stored in cool,dry and dark place.
- During curing water used in the recipe evaporates.
- Lye used in the recipe reduces.
- During curing the weight of the soap reduce by 10%
- Eg 100gm soap when kept to cure,after4-6 weeks it would weigh 90gm.

4.2. Soda ash

- Soda ash form when unsaponified lye reacts with naturally occurring carbon dioxide air.
- It shown on the top layer of the soap.
- To avoid soda ash spray isopropyl alcohol before and after pouring each layer.

5. Results

The soap exhibited good cleaning efficiency in removing microbes on hands. Conclusion:

6. Conclusion

Hence, based on the antimicrobial effects and parameters, the formulated soap can further be standardized and an alternative to commercial medicinal and skin whitening soaps.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All author's declare that they have no conflicts on interest.

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